

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D5.1 – Analysis and recommendations for transformative governance and policy 1

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract		For cities to upscale their climate neutral and resilience objectives for city-wide implementation, the use of governance instruments is essential. adelphi develops a tool/framework for identifying transformative instruments based on city needs. This report presents the status quo of the tool development.		

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Contents

Executive summary.....	6
Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables.....	7
Acronyms.....	8
1 Introduction.....	9
1.1 Purpose and Scope	9
1.2 Document Structure	10
2 Understanding of Transformative Governance	11
2.1 Definitions of governance and transformation.....	11
2.1.1 Governance.....	11
2.1.2 Transformation	12
2.2 Transformative governance instruments.....	14
3 Framework for a transformative governance tool.....	16
3.1 Overall concept for the tool development	16
3.1.1 Analysis of Governance Set-Up.....	16
3.1.2 Identify suitable governance instruments	17
3.1.3 Tool Case Study: Belfast.....	18
3.2 Main steps of the tool development	19
3.3 Possible formats of the final tool	20
References.....	22

Figures

Figure 1: Outcomes of the 5UP approach. Source UP2030 (2023)	9
Figure 2: Fields of transformation (adapated from Schneidewind (2018)) in relation to the three domains of transformation from the 5UP approach from UP2030 (2023)	13
Figure 3: Transformative qualities. Adapted from Hölscher et al. (2020), Visseren-Hamekers et al. (2021), Bressers et al. (2016).....	13
Figure 4: Types of governance instruments. Source: Berger et al. (2007).....	14
Figure 5: Example questions of the governance analysis.....	16
Figure 6: Example results of the governance analysis	17
Figure 7: Basic structure of the best practice database	18
Figure 8: Tool case study Belfast	19
Figure 9: Exemplary tool implementation process for the city of Belfast.....	20

Tables

Table 1: Governance dimensions. Adapted from Bressers et al. (2016).....	12
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Executive summary

In order to reach their climate neutrality and resilience targets, many European cities are currently starting to upscale their pilot initiatives for a city-wide implementation. In such a transformation process from project-based pilot initiatives to standard practices for city administrations and stakeholders, the use of governance instruments is essential. Under the UP2030 Horizon Europe project, adelphi is developing a tool that supports cities in this process by identifying a **mix of transformative governance instruments**. Such **governance instruments** include more conventional “hard” policies (e.g. regulations) but also “soft” policies (e.g. financial incentives, participation, trainings). **Transformative** means that these instruments are designed and implemented in a certain quality (including integrative, inclusive, adaptive, and pluralist criteria) so to enable and drive transformation processes.

The tool being developed by adelphi basically performs a **governance analysis** related to a city’s climate neutrality or resilience objective. **Governance** for this purpose is understood and analysed as the structures and processes of decision-making within a society involving both formal and informal actors. A **relational, multi-actor and multi-level concept of governance** is applied which is essential for transformation processes, as they cannot be managed by single entities such as city administrations. According to the results of the tool’s governance analysis, suitable governance instruments will be proposed with best practice examples.

This report presents the status quo of the tool development. The final deliverable will be the tool accompanied by a report. The format of the final tool is at the moment of this reporting still not defined. It can be web-based or another format (e.g. Excel or PDF file), depending on the results of the engagement process. For this, a maximum of two UP2030 pilot cities will be involved in a co-development and testing approach. In a first step, adelphi elaborated a framework for the tool development, including the governance analysis and a data base of EU-wide best practice governance instruments linking to existing platforms such as Oppla¹ (both being refined continuously). Subsequent steps involve the co-development of the tool with cities and an expert panel, based on online meetings and workshops in presence. The tool elaboration will reflect the cities’ and experts’ feedback on useful contents and formats for a hands-on tool to guide cities in their transformation.

Within the UP2030 project, the transformative governance tool is being developed as part of the upscaling approach, which looks beyond the implementation of pilot initiatives under the project, emphasising the creation of an enabling environment for city-wide implementation, but also for replication by other European cities. Accordingly, experiences from pilot initiatives during the first two years of UP2030 will flow into the tool development during the last year of implementation. The co-development approach however is being implemented in a parallel process, not directly linked to the pilot implementation.

This report serves to provide information on the status quo of the underlying framework of the transformative governance tool. It first provides an understanding of the role of governance in transformation processes. This is followed by a description of the planned governance instruments tool, including the overall concept, the tool development process and ideas for the final output.

¹ www.oppla.eu

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work package’s structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with ICLEI, GGGI, TSPA, among other partners and WP2 (T2.2, T2.3 and T2.4) as well as WP5-T5.3. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
D2.1 The 5UP approach and its contextualisation in the project cities	D3.2 Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 2 D5.3 UP2030 Service platform
MS05 Cities run first workshop on needs MS06 Cities run second workshop on vision MS07 Cities establish user stories MS08 First meeting of the expert panel on Governance and Policy for climate neutrality in European cities	MS14 Cities run second workshop on upscale MS16 Service platform up operative

While this deliverable is a progress report and may serve other consortium partners for information, the final deliverable will target cities in the format of a tool. The development of the tool at the moment of this report is being aligned with the progress on visioning and pathway development as well as individual project stages of pilot cities, possibly Budapest and Belfast (only Budapest confirmed yet).

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
D	Deliverable
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
ICLEI	Local Governments for Sustainability, Resilient Cities Network
MfC	Mapping for Change
MS	Milestone
PPP	Public-private-partnership
TSPA	Thomas Stellmach Planung und Architektur
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The transformative governance tool is being developed by adelphi as part of the UP2030 UP-scaling phase, where “transferability packages and upscaling frameworks related to solutions are prepared to understand and replicate solutions in other cities in Europe and beyond” (UP2030, 2023). Here it relates to the upscaling frameworks, looking into integrative policies, governance barriers as well as multilevel collaboration as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Outcomes of the 5UP approach. Source UP2030 (2023)

In the UP2030 proposal, the deliverable presented with this report is described as “recommendations for transformative governance and policy”. Already, towards the beginning of the programme and up to now, it became clear that cities need more practical guidance on how to use governance effectively to reach their goals of climate neutrality, climate justice and resilience. Particularly when looking at **upscaling pilot initiatives, a wider (i.e. administrative, societal and economic) and long-term transformation process is required** enabling the pathway towards city-wide climate goals.

The current practice often shows that pilot initiatives are planned and implemented like projects by one municipal department, involving other relevant departments and using citizen participation instruments, but within a conventional and linear way of “business as usual” – meaning that overall decision-making processes and structures (i.e. the governance set-up) remain the same. In that way, pilot initiatives can manage and overcome certain challenges and barriers, including for example an uneven distribution of know-how and financial resources, different interests and mindsets, as well as limited ownership and responsibility by the private sector and citizens².

However, when bringing these pilots to a city-wide implementation, “business as usual” overburdens city administrations and possibly creates conflicts of interests and resources. The reason behind it is that such an upscaling procedure requires a transformation process, changing the way cities work in a systemic way. The **UP2030 project supports its pilot cities in the urban transformation as Net-zero cities, Compact cities and Connected cities**. For the purposes of upscaling and replication, additional transformation fields are included in the transformative governance instruments tool (see section 2.1.2).

² mentioned challenges were expressed by experts as well as cities during the course of the project

In order to support cities in the required transformation process, it is necessary to look at their current governance set-up and identify suitable instruments that can drive transformation. For this purpose, the tool provides a first step for cities to analyse their individual governance strengths and challenges in reaching their city-wide climate goals and to receive an orientation on potential governance instruments, including best practice examples.

The transformative governance instruments tool is a work in progress throughout the UP2030 programme, involving consortium partners working on governance in other UP2030 activities, particularly with cities. One to two UP2030 pilot cities are aimed to be involved in a co-development approach, providing consultation on governance to the cities while improving the tool based on the results and feedback from the city engagement. At the time of reporting, Budapest's climate department committed to be engaged in the co-development. While this is not directly linked to the UP2030 pilot of Budapest's "Healthy Streets", the goal is to consult the city administration on how to reach their resilience goals with a focus on heat resilience, based on their governance set-up and with a mix of governance instruments.

The report, while looking into a basic understanding of governance in transformation processes, does not present an in-depth study on this subject. The contents presented on governance and transformation serve to build a literature-based framework for the governance tool being developed by adelphi within the UP2030 programme. Furthermore, the report contains the status quo on the tool development, comprising the framework for a governance analysis – which is the core of the tool – and steps of the tool implementation.

1.2 [Document Structure](#)

The document is organised as follows:

Section 1 -

- ❖ Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure.
- ❖ Section 2 - Understanding of Transformative Governance: a brief introduction to gain an understanding of governance, transformation, and transformative governance instruments.
- ❖ Section 3 - Framework for a transformative governance tool: description of the status quo of the tool development in terms of contents and implementation.

2 Understanding of Transformative Governance

Many European cities are currently in the middle of **multiple transformation processes**, as they commit themselves to city-wide, long-term climate neutrality and climate resilience goals, among other social, environmental and economic goals (Salvia et al. 2023). While smaller pilot projects in these transformation fields have been ongoing over the past years, the challenge now regards their upscaling and mainstreaming. Specific projects so far could be managed by city administrations, often by using external funds and know-how and establishing individual participation processes. However, city-wide implementation puts administrations in a position where project-based management is no longer possible and the established governance set-up hinders or slows down transformation processes. This includes challenges such as:

- **Cities being governed as a place by city administrations** rather than a system (with shared governance among multiple actors), leading to a concentration of responsibilities and ownership;
- **Siloed working processes and know-how** in many urban institutions, inhibiting an integration and mainstreaming of transformative visions, approaches and measures;
- **Outdated, inadequate regulatory instruments** (e.g. building laws and standards), hindering innovative solutions to be implemented at large scale; and
- **Limited financial capacities** of city administrations. (Pascual et al. 2022)

The following section provides a closer look at governance in order to come to an understanding of what it entails and why it is important in transformation processes.

2.1 Definitions of governance and transformation

2.1.1 Governance

Governance in the following pages is understood as the **structures and processes of decision-making** within a society and the implementation of those decisions. It involves both **formal and informal actors** who are engaged in decision-making. Accordingly, governmental institutions are only one of the actors involved in governance, alongside civil society, private sector, researchers, etc. Urban areas usually present a complex scenario, with a wide range of actors and networks involved in urban governance. According to Baud et al. (2021), “because of its own unique political, economic, social and historical context”, each city has a different decision-making arena that is shaped by institutions and multiple actors – in the following this is referred to as the **governance set-up**.

When analysing individual cities’ urban transformation processes, this relational, multi-actor and multi-level understanding of governance is necessary. Based on their unique governance set-up, cities have their individual potentials and individual pathways for driving transformation (Baud et al. 2021). Accordingly, a first step in identifying these potentials and developing suitable pathways is to analyse the status quo of a city’s governance set-up with its **different governance dimensions**.

The governance analysis used for the tool development is based on the Governance Assessment Tool by Bressers et al. (2016). It considers the following governance dimensions and main assessment questions that were partly adopted for the context of the tool development:

Table 1: Governance dimensions. Adapted from Bressers et al. (2016)

Governance dimensions	Main descriptive question
Levels and scales	Which administrative levels are involved and how?
Actors and networks	Which actors are involved in the process and what is their role? To what extent do they have network relationships?
Problem perspective and goal ambitions	Which various angles does the debate of public and stakeholders take towards the problem at hand? How do current policies reflect these perspectives?
Strategies and instruments	Which policy instruments and measures are used to modify the problem situation? Is a policy mix of different policy types used, e.g. legal, informational, partnering (see section 2.2)
Responsibilities and resources	What government and non-government actors have responsibility for what tasks under the relevant policies and municipal practices? What legal authorities and resources they have available for this purpose?

Section 3.1.1 provides more details of the tool’s governance analysis based on these five governance dimensions.

2.1.2 Transformation

Transformation is a broad term used in different disciplines and it refers to “the notion of **systemic, essential, and radical change**” (Elmqvist et al. 2018). Since the UP2030 project task is to support cities in achieving the EU climate neutrality targets and strengthening their resilience to climate change, the transformation processes are addressing the changes in this respective field. With regard to urban space, transformation can concern not only the what, but also the how.

The "**what**" is about the transformation fields in which climate action (mitigation of emissions and adaptation) could be achieved. These fields are targeted in the three transformation domains (net-zero city, connected city and compact city) which were defined within the UP2030 project, to find a common ground for all pilot cities and cluster their objectives. Given that the objective of task 5.1 is to make recommendations for policy instruments and best practices for upscaling, it was decided to break down these domains in a more granular and tangible way for cities. In the context of urban transformation, **six** key areas were identified as **fields of transformation**: mobility sector, climate-resilient urban development, energy sector, circular economy, water management and social and health spatial planning (adapted from Schneidewind 2018, Figure 2).

Figure 2: Fields of transformation (adapted from Schneidewind (2018)) in relation to the three domains of transformation from the 5UP approach from UP2030 (2023)

For the "how", different scientific publications (Hölscher et al. (2020), Visseren-Hamekers et al. (2021), Bressers et al. (2016)) were analysed to examine what **quality criteria** classify processes as "transformative". The publications presented different criteria, some of which overlapped. As a result, these were summarised under the following six transformative qualities and are presented in **Error! Reference source not found..** They can be described as follows:

1. Integrative	Integrative: Bringing together different perspectives and interests while breaking down silos and fostering collaboration across different sectors and departments.
2. Inclusive	Inclusive: Ensuring that all relevant stakeholders, including marginalised groups, have a voice and representation in decision-making processes.
3. Adaptive	Adaptive: Responding and adjusting to changing circumstances, uncertainties, and feedback over time.
4. Pluralist	Pluralist: Recognising and accepting diverse values, beliefs, and ideologies within governance frameworks to foster a more tolerant and democratic society.
5. Long-term	
6. Intensive (effective, sufficient)	

Figure 3: Transformative qualities. Adapted from Hölscher et al. (2020), Visseren-Hamekers et al. (2021), Bressers et al. (2016)

Long-term: Considering the future implications and sustainability of decisions rather than focusing solely on short-term gains.

Intensive (effective, sufficient): Dedication of significant resources, effort, and attention to governance processes to ensure their effectiveness and adequacy in achieving desired outcomes.

Based on the transformation fields and the transformative qualities, it can be concluded that transformative governance “(...) manages regime shifts across multiple scales in social–ecological systems while encouraging social change and innovation” (Pascual et al. 2022).

2.2 Transformative governance instruments

The objective of the transformative governance instrument tool is to propose a mix of governance instruments that supports cities in their transformation process. Following the relational and multi-actor understanding of governance, relevant instruments also take this perspective and go beyond purely government-driven regulations. While legal instruments are still recognised as highly important and effective, “**soft instruments**” are seen as crucial for strengthening shared governance, distributing responsibilities and resources among various stakeholders. Considering that transformation is not an administrative or political process but one that includes societies and economies, this emphasis on multi-actor, shared governance is key.

Figure 4 provides an overview of different **types of governance instruments**, including regulatory, soft and hybrid instruments:

Figure 4: Types of governance instruments. Source: Berger et al. (2007)

This overview shows that cities dispose of a diverse set of supporting instruments to regulate, inform, engage or distribute responsibilities among stakeholders in order to achieve certain goals.

To make sure that **governance instruments have the quality to support transformation**, the criteria mentioned in

are applicable. In that way, a Municipal Building Code (often being one of the legal instruments with a very low transformative quality) would need to integrate different principles such as climate neutrality and social justice, while ensuring technical standards and the legal quality of land and its usability. At the same time, awareness raising campaigns and guidelines, e.g. for green roofs, would consider multiple aspects such as rainwater retention, insulation and biodiversity, while looking into different investment capacities of landlords and informing about funding opportunities.

For each city and transformation context, a suitable mix of governance instruments needs to be identified and developed. Instruments need to be designed individually in order to respond to the specific governance set-up and the specific transformation goals to be reached in a city. Nevertheless, the purpose of adelphi's governance tool to provide general recommendations with best practice examples serves as an orientation for city administrations and stakeholders to know what kind of governance instruments are most relevant for their transformation process in order to reach their goals.

3 Framework for a transformative governance tool

3.1 Overall concept for the tool development

The transformative governance tool aims at supporting cities in their ambitions to reach specific transformation goals, focusing mainly on the areas of climate neutrality, climate justice and urban climate resilience. It can be applied by city administrations at a starting point of a transformation process (e.g. when defining pathways or action programs) or at mid-term (e.g. to evaluate an ongoing process).

The core element of the tool is an **analysis of the current governance set-up** regarding a specific transformation goal that is A) changing the status quo to become climate neutral, climate resilient and/ or socially just; and/ or B) scaling-up pilot initiatives to city-wide implementation.

Based on this governance analysis, the tool will then:

- **analyse a city’s governance strengths and gaps** (or potentials); and
- **identify suitable governance instruments** that support the city administration and other involved actors to reach the transformation goals.

In the following sections, these three elements of the tool are presented.

3.1.1 Analysis of Governance Set-Up

The analysis of the governance set-up (also: governance analysis) considers five governance dimensions (see Table 1) and assesses up to which degree established decision-making processes and structures in the city can drive or hinder the envisioned transformation. For this purpose, a set of key questions are being (co-)developed for each governance dimension, referring to the above transformation criteria. Figure 5 provides an example of questions. A more extensive set of questions are in the process of being developed, in a way that they can be scored.

Figure 5: Example questions of the governance analysis

The scoring of answers is required to present results in a scalable way (e.g. low-medium-high), indicating strong governance dimensions as well as gaps. The scores relate to the quality of a governance dimension according to the transformative criteria. Accordingly, gaps can identify areas where the status quo of the

governance set-up may hinder transformation. In a summarised way, the results could be presented as in Figure 6. In addition, a description of the results for each governance dimension will be provided.

Figure 6: Example results of the governance analysis

3.1.2 Identify suitable governance instruments

Based on the results of the governance analysis, a set of governance instruments is identified that aims at **using existing strengths** and **closing relevant gaps** to enable and drive transformation processes. A **mix of instrument types** will be aimed at with “hard” and “soft” instruments, allowing for regulatory changes (with high effectiveness) as well as awareness and behavioural changes (with increased ownership and shared governance). The exact procedure and output of the tool to attribute governance instruments to strengths and gaps will be elaborated with the cities.

In order to provide a better orientation in terms of “real life” examples, an Excel-based **database of best practices for different governance instruments** in different fields of transformation is provided. Suitable examples are linked to the proposed instruments. Furthermore, city stakeholders will have the opportunity to search for best practice examples in the database on their own account. Excel is being used as it is a tool all city stakeholders are familiar with and could be shared easily. The basic structure of the database is presented in Figure 7.

Project	Instrument type	Where	Strengths	Gaps	Duration	Color Code Spectrum of Realities	Instruments	Gaps
A Square in Every Neighborhood - Lisbon Interface Hub	Financial / economic					Soft Law	Informational / endorsing	Goals & Perspectives
Territorial Ordering Plan (POT) of Bogotá 2022-2035 "The greening of Bogotá" Inter	Partnering						Partnering	Actors & Networks
Local Climate Change Plan for the Province of Lima - Peru Interface Hub	Legal / mandating						Financial / economic	Resources & Responsibility
Dare to Dream of a Green River - Antwerp Interface Hub	Legal / mandating						Legal / mandating	Levels & Scales
Urban Green Network - Quito Interface Hub	Legal / mandating					Regulatory	Strategical	Strategies & Instruments
Urban Traffic Plan - Rotterdam Interface Hub	Legal / mandating							
Biotope Area Factor - Berlin Interface Hub	Legal / mandating							
Guide for the design and construction of infrastructure of the National System of Protected Area	Legal / mandating							
Plan de uso y gestión de suelo 2021-2033 del Distrito Metropolitano de Quito Interface Hub	Legal / mandating							
Green Neighborhood (Manzana Verde) architectural innovation contest - Malaga Interface Hub	Informational / endorsing							
Masterplan Parkbogen Ost - Leipzig Interface Hub	Legal / mandating							
Sponsorship Programme for Public Spaces in Quito Interface Hub	Partnering							
Monteria Climate Change Plan Interface Hub	Legal / mandating							
Tempelhofer Feld development and restoration plan - Berlin Interface Hub	Partnering							

Figure 7: Basic structure of the best practice database

3.1.3 Tool Case Study: Belfast

For a better understanding of how the tool works and about its benefits, an example is provided for its possible application with the City of Belfast’s Net-Zero Districts Approach. Within UP2030, Belfast is being supported in the implementation of measures to reach their climate-neutrality targets in the Linen Quarter, a central District of the city with residential and commercial areas. This approach should also be applied city-wide in the long term (beyond UP2030).

Figure 8 visualises the context of Belfast’s upscaling ambitions and how the governance tool can support this process. For city-wide implementation, Belfast’s planned pathway might foresee to test the approach in the Linen Quarter first and then use the gained experience to apply it in other Districts in the same or in an improved way. While the application in one District may have already shown certain challenges that can be overcome by the city administration, city-wide implementation is likely to show further challenges. This is due to the fact that the **governance set-up becomes more complex with more stakeholders involved and more structures and processes** required. To take one example, conflicting interests and different mindsets within the city administration but also among city stakeholders might become more difficult to manage.

Figure 8: Tool case study Belfast

In this setting, the tool will consider the different **governance dimensions with a multi-stakeholder perspective** and analyse if e.g. stakeholders share the same goals and visions and how knowledge and responsibilities are distributed. Based on the results, it will be possible to identify where the city has strong areas of governance and where certain gaps appear, often related to the challenges the city is facing. In order to propose suitable governance instruments, it is relevant to both use existing strengths as a driver of transformation and to reduce gaps. If, e.g. citizen information and participation are already high, the existing structures and processes should be reinforced through additional or more innovative instruments such as co-designing approaches that allow citizens to be an active part of District planning. If, e.g. mandates and resources are weak (due to fragmented governance of Belfast), the establishment of public-private-partnerships (PPPs) and resident groups could allow for a better share of responsibilities and resources. For these more general instruments proposed, specific examples will then be provided based on best practices from other European cities.

3.2 Main steps of the tool development

The transformative governance tool is being developed based on a desktop research, in which different concepts of governance, transformation and climate governance were analysed, together with applied governance assessment methods, to establish a basic framework. The tool development also involves an expert panel at key points of the work progress as well as one to two pilot cities in a co-development approach (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Exemplary tool implementation process for the city of Belfast

To support the desktop research an **expert panel** has been composed by experts who are working on urban governance aspects in different transformation contexts and experts from the UP2030 consortium. At least one online meeting is foreseen per year to discuss the status of the tool development with the experts and receive their feedback. Contacts have been established with several experts, who already provided inputs and first feedback during individual calls. The first expert panel meeting was held on October 13, 2023, including participants from GGGI (Global Green Growth Institute), TSPA (Thomas Stellmach Planung und Architektur), ICLEI (Local Governments for Sustainability, Resilient Cities Network) and a freelance expert. The outcomes of this event emphasised the following key points for further tool development:

- Firstly, it is crucial for best practices and instruments to clearly state the effort and time needed for their implementation. This helps determine if there is an additional requirement for significant resources.
- Secondly, there was a suggestion for a tool to automatically generate a simple report (e.g. in a PDF-format).
- Finally: The success of such a tool depends on its ability to translate complex scientific findings into practical actions for cities.

The date for the next expert panel meeting has not yet been set, but it is expected to take place after the first workshops have been held in the pilot cities.

The co-development with cities is foreseen to take place starting in May 2024. While the workshops are an in-depth governance assessment and already provide consultancy to the cities going beyond the tool's purpose, adelphi will use them to test the current framework and receive important feedback on city needs regarding the tool's contents and design.

3.3 Possible formats of the final tool

As the tool is to be developed jointly with the pilot cities, only the basic framework has been developed so far. It will probably be a type of survey format, but it is not yet clear exactly how it can be implemented technically. The format should help cities to identify their gaps and assets quickly and easily, which also

means that visualisations and/or animations should probably support this. As also emphasised in the expert panel, the results could be transferred into a report form. Since task 5.3 could follow a similar logic with a tool for "Financing the Transition", synergies will be sought in the course of the project to see whether similar approaches would be helpful for the two tasks. There is also an additional partner, Mapping for Change (MfC), which has developed a tool via the Notion platform that also has functionalities that would be useful for governance analysis and issuing recommendations. It is to be expected that the workshop with at least one of the pilot cities, the exchange with GGGI and possibly MfC, the Strategic Learning Taskforce and the expert panel in particular will make the design of the tool more concrete in the coming months.

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